

U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service

ECOS

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California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*)

[Range Information](#) | [Candidate Info](#) | [Federal Register](#) | [Recovery](#) | [Critical Habitat](#) | [SSA](#) | [Conservation Plans](#) | [Petitions](#) | [Biological Opinions](#) | [Life History](#)

Taxonomy: [View taxonomy in ITIS](#)

Listing Status: Endangered

Where Listed: WHEREVER FOUND

General Information

The California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) is one of the largest rails (family Rallidae), measuring 13-19 inches from bill to tail. It is characterized by its hen-like appearance, a long, slightly downward-curving bill, olive-brown upper parts, a cinnamon-buff colored breast, dark flanks crossed by white bars and white undertail coverts which are often exposed when the bird is agitated.

Current Listing Status Summary

Show entries

Status	Date Listed	Lead Region	Where Listed
Endangered	10-13-1970	Pacific Southwest Region (Region 8)	Wherever found Additional species inform:

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» Range Information

Current Range

[Last Updated: 03-19-2018](#) - *Wherever found*

Zoom in! Some species' locations may be small and hard to see from a wide perspective. To narrow-in on locations, check the state and county lists (below) and then use the zoom tool.

Want the FWS's current range for all species? Click [here](#) to download a zip file containing all individual shapefiles and metadata for all species.

* For consultation needs do not use only this current range map, please use [IPaC](#).

Current range maps are only shown within the jurisdictional boundaries of the United States of America. The species may also occur outside this region.

• **Wherever found**

Listing status: Endangered

- **States/US Territories** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: California
- **US Counties** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: [View All](#)
- **USFWS Refuges** in which this population is known to occur: Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge, San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge

» **Candidate Information**

No Candidate information available for this species.

No Candidate Assessments available for this species.

No Candidate Notice of Review Documents currently available for this species.

No Uplisting Documents currently available for this species.

» **Federal Register Documents**

Federal Register Documents

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title	Support Docum
10/16/2024	89 FR 83510 83514	Initiation of 5-Year Status Reviews for 59 Pacific Southwest Species	
07/31/2023	88 FR 49310 49355	General Provisions; Revised List of Migratory Birds (& taxonomic corrections for 9 ESA-listed species)	
06/18/2018	83 FR 28251 28254	Initiation of 5-Year Status Reviews of 50 Species in California, Nevada, and the Klamath Basin of Oregon	
02/26/2014	79 FR 10830 10831	Notice of Availability; Final Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California	• Recor
05/21/2010	75 FR 28636 28642	Initiation of 5-Year Reviews of 34 Species in California and Nevada; Availability of 96 Completed 5-Year Reviews in California and Nevada	
02/10/2010	75 FR 6696 6697	Draft Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California	
10/13/1970	35 FR 16047 16048	Appendix D - United States List of Endangered Native Fish and Wildlife; 35 FR 16047 16048	
08/25/1970	35 FR 13519 13520	Notice of Proposed Rule Making.(Conservation of Endangered Species and Other Fish or Wildlife)	

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» **Species Status Assessments (SSAs)**

Species Status Assessments (SSAs)

No Species Status Assessments (SSA's) are currently available for this species.

Special Rule Publications

No Special Rule Publications currently available for this species.

» Recovery

- [Species with Recovery Documents Data Explorer](#)
- Recovery Priority Number: 3C

Current Recovery Plan(s)

Show entries

Date	Plan Stage	Recovery Plan	Implementation Status	SSAs/Biological Reports	Recovery Implementa Strategies
08/27/2013	Final Revision 1	Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California	View Implementation Progress		

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

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Other Recovery Documents

Note: This report includes actual Five Year Review completions and notices as well as records that act as Five Year Review completions and notices.

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title	Document Type
10/16/2024	89 FR 83510 83514	Initiation of 5-Year Status Reviews for 59 Pacific Southwest Species	• Five Year Review Information Soli
06/18/2018	83 FR 28251 28254	Initiation of 5-Year Status Reviews of 50 Species in California, Nevada, and the Klamath Basin of Oregon	• Five Year Review Information Soli
02/26/2014	79 FR 10830 10831	Notice of Availability: Final Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California	• Recovery Plan Fi Availability (non-
05/21/2010	75 FR 28636 28642	Initiation of 5-Year Reviews of 34 Species in California and Nevada; Availability of 96 Completed 5-Year Reviews in California and Nevada	• Five Year Review Information Soli
02/10/2010	75 FR 6696 6697	Draft Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California	• Recovery Plan D Availability (non-

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Five Year Reviews

Note: This report includes actual Five Year Review completions as well as records that act as Five Year Review completions.

Show entries

Date	Title
08/27/2025	California Ridgway's Rail 5YR 2025
08/31/2020	California clapper rail(<i>Rallus longirostris obsoletus</i>) 5-Year Review

04/29/2013 California clapper rail(*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) 5 Year Review

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No Delisting Documents currently available for this species.

» Critical Habitat

No Critical Habitat Documents currently available for this species.

» Conservation Plans

Habitat Conservation Plans (HCP) ([learn more](#))

Show entries

HCP Plan Summaries

[PG&E Bay Area Operations and Maintenance HCP](#)

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

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» Petitions

No Petitions currently available for this species.

» Biological Opinions

To see all FWS Issued Biological Opinions please visit the [BO Report](#).

» Life History

No Life History information has been entered into this system for this species.

» Other Resources

[NatureServe Explorer Species Reports](#)-- NatureServe Explorer is a source for authoritative conservation information on more than 50,000 plants, animals and ecological communities of the U.S and Canada. NatureServe Explorer provides in-depth information on rare and endangered species, but includes common plants and animals too. NatureServe Explorer is a product of NatureServe in collaboration with the Natural Heritage Network.

[ITIS Reports](#)-- ITIS (the Integrated Taxonomic Information System) is a source for authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes of North America and the world.

[FWS Digital Media Library](#) -- The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's National Digital Library is a searchable collection of selected images, historical artifacts, audio clips, publications, and video." +